

SUPPLEMENTARY FILE S1

Comprehensive UMI-based error-corrected sequencing pipeline

Overview

This document provides a complete command-level documentation of a UMI-based analysis pipeline of the associated methods article. Every processing step present in the original batch script is represented here, including environment setup, data preparation, UMI extraction, alignment, consensus calling, deduplication, metadata preservation, and final filtering emphasizing reproducibility and traceability.

Software tools and version

Software	Version
BWA	0.7.17-r1188
Fgbio	2.0.2
Picard	2.22.3
Samtools	1.6

FASTQ to unaligned BAM conversion

Paired-end FASTQ files are converted to an unaligned BAM file using Picard. This assigns sample metadata and provides a BAM container for UMI extraction.

Command:

```
picard FastqToSam \  
FASTQ=<SAMPLE_R1.fastq.gz> \  
FASTQ2=<SAMPLE_R2.fastq.gz> \  
O=<SAMPLE>_unmapped.bam \  
SM=<SAMPLE_ID>
```

UMI extraction and tagging

UMI sequences are extracted from reads based on a defined read structure ("5M2S+T 5M2S+T" for Illumina and MGI) and stored in BAM tags for downstream grouping. Make sure to provide sufficient resources to Fgbio.

Command:

```
fgbio ExtractUmisFromBam \  
--input=<SAMPLE>_unmapped.bam \  
--output=<SAMPLE>_unmapped_withUMI.bam \  
--read-structure=<READ_STRUCTURE> \  
--molecular-index-tags=ZA ZB \  
--single-tag=RX
```

Unaligned BAM to FASTQ conversion

UMI-tagged BAM files are converted back to interleaved FASTQ format for alignment.

Command:

```
picard SamToFastq \  
  INPUT=<SAMPLE>_unmapped_withUMI.bam \  
  FASTQ=<SAMPLE>_withUMI.fastq.gz \  
  INTERLEAVE=true \  
  INCLUDE_NON_PF_READS=false
```

Alignment of UMI-tagged reads

Reads are aligned to the reference genome using BWA-MEM and sorted.

Command:

```
bwa mem -p -t 8 <REFERENCE_GENOME.fa> <SAMPLE>_withUMI.fastq.gz | \  
samtools sort -@ 8 -o <SAMPLE>_unmergedUMI.bam
```

Merge aligned and unaligned BAMs (applicable for DC and MC)

Alignment information is merged with the original unaligned BAM to retain UMI tags.

Commands:

```
picard MergeBamAlignment \  
  ALIGNED=<SAMPLE>_unmergedUMI.bam \  
  UNMAPPED=<SAMPLE>_unmapped_withUMI.bam \  
  OUTPUT=<SAMPLE>_UMImerged.bam \  
  REFERENCE_SEQUENCE=<REFERENCE_GENOME.fa> \  
  MAX_GAPS=-1 \  
  CLIP_ADAPTERS=false \  
  SORT_ORDER=coordinate \  
  EXPECTED_ORIENTATIONS=FR \  
  VALIDATION_STRINGENCY=SILENT \  
  CREATE_INDEX=true \  
  ALIGNER_PROPER_PAIR_FLAGS=false
```

Group reads by UMI

Reads are grouped by UMI sequence and genomic position to define molecular families.

Make sure to provide sufficient resources to Fgbio.

Command:

```
fgbio GroupReadsByUmi \  
  --strategy=paired \  
  --input=<SAMPLE>_UMImerged.bam \  
  --output=<SAMPLE>_UMIgrouped.bam \  
  --raw-tag=RX
```

```
--min-map-q=10 \  
--edits=1
```

Duplex consensus read generation

Duplex consensus reads are generated to suppress strand-specific sequencing errors.

Command:

```
fgbio CallDuplexConsensusReads \  
--input=<SAMPLE>_UMIgrouped.bam \  
--output=<SAMPLE>_unaligned_DC.bam \  
--error-rate-pre-umi=45 \  
--error-rate-post-umi=30 \  
--min-input-base-quality=30 \  
--min-reads 2 1 1
```

Molecular consensus read generation

Molecular consensus reads are generated independently of strand pairing.

Command:

```
fgbio CallMolecularConsensusReads \  
--input=<SAMPLE>_UMIgrouped.bam \  
--output=<SAMPLE>_unaligned_MC.bam \  
--rejects=<SAMPLE>_MC_rejected.bam \  
--error-rate-pre-umi=45 \  
--error-rate-post-umi=30 \  
--min-consensus-base-quality=40 \  
--min-input-base-quality=30 \  
--min-reads=1
```

Realignment of consensus reads (applicable to DC and MC)

Consensus BAM files are converted to FASTQ, aligned, and sorted.

Command:

```
picard SamToFastq \  
INPUT=<SAMPLE>_unaligned_<DC/MC>.bam \  
FASTQ=<SAMPLE>_unaligned_<DC/MC>.fastq.gz \  
INTERLEAVE=true \  
INCLUDE_NON_PF_READS=false  
  
bwa mem \  
-p -t <THREADS> \  
<REFERENCE_GENOME.fa> \  
<SAMPLE>_unaligned_<DC/MC>.fastq.gz \  
| samtools sort \  
-@ <THREADS> \  
-o <SAMPLE>_aligned_<DC/MC>.bam
```

Metadata-preserving BAM merging and read group assignment (applicable to DC and MC)

Aligned and unaligned consensus BAM files are merged and annotated with read groups to retain UMI metadata.

Commands:

Sort aligned and unaligned BAMs by query name

```
picard SortSam \  
INPUT=<SAMPLE>_aligned_<DC/MC>.bam \  
OUTPUT=<SAMPLE>_aligned_<DC/MC>_query.bam \  
SORT_ORDER=queryname
```

```
picard SortSam \  
INPUT=<SAMPLE>_unaligned_<DC/MC>.bam \  
OUTPUT=<SAMPLE>_unaligned_<DC/MC>_query.bam \  
SORT_ORDER=queryname
```

Merge aligned and unaligned consensus BAMs

```
picard MergeBamAlignment \  
VALIDATION_STRINGENCY=SILENT \  
UNMAPPED=<SAMPLE>_unaligned_<DC/MC>_query.bam \  
ALIGNED=<SAMPLE>_aligned_<DC/MC>_query.bam \  
OUTPUT=<SAMPLE>_merged_no_read_group_<DC/MC>.bam \  
REFERENCE_SEQUENCE=<REFERENCE_GENOME.fa> \  
CLIP_ADAPTERS=false \  
CREATE_INDEX=true \  
EXPECTED_ORIENTATIONS=FR \  
MAX_GAPS=-1 \  
SORT_ORDER=coordinate \  
ALIGNER_PROPER_PAIR_FLAGS=false \  
ATTRIBUTES_TO_RETAIN=X0 \  
ATTRIBUTES_TO_RETAIN=ZS \  
ATTRIBUTES_TO_RETAIN=ZI \  
ATTRIBUTES_TO_RETAIN=ZM \  
ATTRIBUTES_TO_RETAIN=ZC \  
ATTRIBUTES_TO_RETAIN=ZN \  
ATTRIBUTES_TO_RETAIN=ad \  
ATTRIBUTES_TO_RETAIN=bd \  
ATTRIBUTES_TO_RETAIN=cd \  
ATTRIBUTES_TO_RETAIN=ae \  
ATTRIBUTES_TO_RETAIN=be \  
ATTRIBUTES_TO_RETAIN=ce
```

Add or replace read groups

```
picard AddOrReplaceReadGroups \  
INPUT=<SAMPLE>_merged_no_read_group_<DC/MC>.bam \  
OUTPUT=<SAMPLE>_merged_no_read_group_<DC/MC>_query.bam
```

```
OUTPUT=<SAMPLE>_<CONSENSUS_TYPE>_aligned_merged.bam \  
RGID=<SAMPLE> \  
RGLB=<LIBRARY> \  
RGPL=<PLATFORM> \  
RGSM=<SAMPLE> \  
RGPU=<PLATFORM_UNIT>
```

Final coordinate sorting and indexing

```
samtools sort \  
<SAMPLE>_<DC/MC>_aligned_merged.bam \  
-o <SAMPLE>_<DC/MC>_aligned_merged_sorted.bam
```

```
samtools index \  
<SAMPLE>_<DC/MC>_aligned_merged_sorted.bam
```

14. Consensus read filtering

High-stringency filtering removes low-confidence consensus reads using fgbio.

Command:

Filtering for DC

```
samtools sort -n <SAMPLE>_DC_aligned_merged_sorted.bam | \  
fgbio FilterConsensusReads \  
--input=/dev/stdin \  
--output=/dev/stdout \  
--ref=<REFERENCE_GENOME.fa> \  
--min-reads 2 1 1 \  
--max-read-error-rate=0.05 \  
--max-base-error-rate=0.1 \  
--min-base-quality=50 \  
--max-no-call-fraction=0.05 \  
--require-single-strand-agreement=true | \  
samtools sort -o <SAMPLE>_DC_aligned_merged_sorted_filtered.bam
```

Filtering for MC

```
samtools sort -n <SAMPLE>_mol_consensus_aligned_merged_sorted.bam | \  
fgbio FilterConsensusReads \  
--input=/dev/stdin \  
--output=/dev/stdout \  
--ref=<REFERENCE_GENOME.fa> \  
--min-reads 3 \  
--max-read-error-rate=0.05 \  
--max-base-error-rate=0.1 \  
--min-base-quality=40 \  
--max-no-call-fraction=0.1 | \  
samtools sort -o <SAMPLE>_mol_consensus_aligned_merged_sorted_filtered.bam
```

Final outputs

This pipeline produces indexed and UMI-tagged BAM files containing filtered duplex and molecular consensus reads. These files are suitable for downstream ultra-rare variant calling and quantitative analyses.